

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF VALUES IN THE FAMILY

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ABSTRACT

The article reveals the role of values in family relations, its social and psychological aspects, the use of values to ensure family stability, and the extent to which the formation of a person's spiritual and educational image depends on family values. At the same time, it is highlighted how much family relationships influence the values of a person.

At all stages of human development, the family and its fundamental foundations have become important for the development of society and the development of the individual. Taking into account that the first stage of human socialization is the family, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "Young people have independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential, and are people who are not inferior to their peers in any field on a global scale. We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that he can grow up and be happy. {1}

Since the creation of humanity, it has been looking for comfortable conditions, a safe place for itself, and for survival, it has been looking for teammates similar to itself, with close ties. A person's desire to live as a couple, to see himself in a certain group, to communicate with loved ones made it possible for the first family and marriage relationships to emerge.

Due to the changes in the division of labor, the development of agriculture, animal husbandry and handicrafts, the adaptation and specialization of the sexes to professions, the mutual relations in the family also change.

Through the establishment of private property relations, a group of relatives with their own territorial units and inherited properties is formed. After that, communities specializing in a certain profession and the rise of property inequality began to separate the residences of the rich nobles and representatives of the poor class.

The birth and development of the family also required a certain social environment. It may not be enough to form a small family consisting only of spouses and children through property separation and inheritance relations. In this regard, we believe that some principles of humanity, a special process connected with the human thinking of the desire for a family worked. In our opinion, it is not possible to start the process of family formation only with the satisfaction of sexual desires, the rules of seed breeding and the taboos of tribes on a certain

relationship. Because even in the primitive clan and tribal times, the leaders of these groups also need to have family relationships in addition to physical strength or power to hold their teammates around them. This makes it possible to conclude that the stages of family formation in the history of mankind are fundamentally different from the way animals live and live in pairs.

The main condition for the formation of marital relations is the needs for these relations and obligations reflected in social views. At the heart of these needs are the peculiarities of the individual lifestyle of a person, which sometimes arises due to biological (mating, having children), and sometimes social (getting rid of loneliness, creating or strengthening a position) needs. This is the first factor in the formation of family and marriage relationships, and the primacy of a person's sexual and physical inclinations is often manifested at the base of primary needs and social obligations. However, family relationships also have an emotional basis that is not pre-intended and not tied to any sexual inclinations, which makes a person's views on family and family relationships strong emotional views, love and affection, sanctity, self-sacrifice, loyalty. connects with them. On the basis of high psychological emotions lies the highest peak of self-awareness of a person, aspirations for human perfection directed at high emotional goals. These aspirations arise from moral and religious belief levels, communication skills, and motivational characteristics toward family and marital relationships. Parents', especially mother's, worries about the baby can be explained by the term "loving relationship" in psychology. As the baby grows, the meaning of this word expands by itself. The expansion of interpersonal relations in the family, the deepening of the relationship of the triad of father, mother and child leads to the formation of loving relations in parents as an experience. The initial communication and loving relationship between the parents and the baby takes place in a physiological form, that is, when the mother first holds the baby in her arms, holds it in her arms, moves it safely, the occurrence of a good or bad psychological relationship in the child. provides.[2]

Among the most important stages of communication between family members, the following can be distinguished:

- Psychological environment before the formation of the family. Feeling the need for a family and transitioning to concrete relationships;
- Emergence of socio-economic agreement and contractual features in entering into family relations. Determining the rights and obligations of family members in advance;
- The stage of recognition and support of the family by society. Emergence of looking at the family as a part of the society;
- The emergence of complex social relations between families, knowledge of the right of inheritance and the socialization stage of parent-child relations;
- Introduction and implementation of the norms of the society and the state in marital, parental and child relations;
- Separation of the main task of the family in raising children with education in educational institutions, etc.

If we briefly analyze the main social, spiritual, moral and psychological tasks of the family, all the feelings that are formed in a person: the buds of kindness, consistency,

responsibility towards oneself and the environment are manifested in the family. . For this reason, the family is also called the primary basis of socialization in foreign literature.

It is known that a person is formed on the basis of social and interpersonal relations, which is a product of these relations. Also, a person is the subject and creator of conscious activity. The most important definition of a person in the family is that he is directly related to the complex social relations in the society, that he is both an object and a subject in relation to social activities at the same time.

Every person cannot feel the feeling of the Motherland in the literal sense without understanding the role and functions of the family in the society, the value of the family, without understanding that the Motherland begins at the threshold. This work is mainly about the traditions of upbringing in every Uzbek family and their improvement, turning national values into an integral part of the lifestyle, harmonizing modern forms of communication culture with Eastern forms, education of work, its important principle of a happy marriage for children. can be realized by achieving appreciation. The family, as a multifunctional social institution, exerts its influence on every activity of the society. It can be said that the principles common to all members of the family are embodied in the institution of the family through the direct participation of the person in education and upbringing. That is why all the principles formed in the institution of the family and raised to the level of value occupy a leading place in the life of society. Regardless of the content of these values, they serve as the main means of expressing the social, economic, political, spiritual, moral and religious origin, national and universal character of a person.

It is difficult to imagine the national values of each nation without its history, spirituality, culture, unique customs and traditions. "When we say value, we should understand a set of natural and social benefits and events that serve the interests and goals of the nation, people and social groups, which are important for people and humanity, and are valued and appreciated by them."

In general, the spiritual image of the young generation, their behavior and behavior begins with the culture of family relations. Every person, regardless of whether he is big or small, expresses his feelings, inner feelings, and hopes in the process of relationships. That is why the development of society, the formation of people as a whole, occurs in their interaction, cooperation, and interaction with each other.

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